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Research Article

Design And in Silico Screening of Thiazolidine-2,4-Dione Analogs as Potential Aldose Reductase Inhibitors

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ABSTRACT

Defective insulin secretion and resistance to insulin action leads to diabetes mellitus. The oral hypoglycemic agents, such as thiazolidinediones (PPAR γ agonists) attenuate insulin resistance. Despite the use of well-planned dosage regimens of oral hypoglycemic agents/insulin or both, the prevention and control of this pathological condition is still a challenging task. There are numerous thiazolidinediones available in the chemical space which are still not explored for their therapeutic efficacy. Implementation of rational approaches makes the drug discovery process more goal-oriented and saves resources in terms of time and money. By considering the ongoing research on Aldose reductase inhibitors as antidiabetic agents, fifty thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogs (1-50) were designed to investigate their in silico drug-likeness profile and in silico binding pattern with Aldose reductase inhibitor receptor. Online tools, such as molinspiration and SwissADME were utilized to calculate drug-likeness properties of the designed compounds. All the compounds were found to obey the Lipinski Rule of Five and some of them have shown violations, indicating their good oral absorption. Calculation of synthetic accessibility score and bioavailability score of the selected compounds enabled us to understand the structure complexity, feasibility in their synthesis and their predicted bioavailability. Docking studies of ligands 1-50 was performed by using 1PWM, 1PWL as target protein (Aldose reductase inhibitor isoform) and marketed thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogue, Fidarestat, Minalrestat respectively as a reference compound. The results indicated that interaction of ligand with key amino acid residues, TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300 was important as they were observed in the docking analysis of reference Fidarestat, Minalrestat. The binding pattern of compounds 8, 14 and 15 were found to be similar to Fidarestat, Minalrestat.

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Thus, the outcomes of the study demonstrated the in-silico potential of above mentioned compounds as Aldose reductase inhibitors.

INTRODUCTION

Drug discovery and development is a complex, time-consuming, and multidisciplinary process. The conventional method of drug discovery involves a traditional approach where new pharmaceutical compounds are identified and developed through a sequence of experimental and trial-based procedures. However, recent advancements in computational technologies have revolutionized these processes, offering significant improvements in efficiency and precision in the field of drug discovery and development.¹⁻³

Drug failure can result from factors like lack of effectiveness, side effects, poor pharmacokinetics, and market limitations. Recently, *in-silico* chemistry and molecular modeling have become popular in computer-aided drug design. Drug likeness refers to a balance of molecular properties and structural features, such as hydrophobicity, electronic distribution, hydrogen bonding, size, and flexibility, which make a molecule similar to existing drugs. Rules like Lipinski's Rule of Five (RO5) help predict key pharmacokinetic properties, including absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion. These properties can be estimated from a molecule's structure before synthesis, streamlining the drug development process.⁴⁻⁶

Intermolecular interactions in protein-drug complexes are crucial and require complex modeling. Docking simulations predict how drug candidates bind to protein targets, usually keeping the protein rigid while allowing the ligand to

adapt. Computational tools have transformed research by increasing efficiency, providing insights, and helping solve complex problems that traditional methods struggle to address.⁷⁻⁹

Aldose reductase enzyme inhibitors play a crucial role in managing complications associated with diabetes mellitus. Aldose reductase is the key enzyme in the polyol pathway, responsible for converting glucose to sorbitol (Figure 1). In individuals with diabetes, excess glucose is shunted into this pathway, leading to the accumulation of sorbitol in tissues. This accumulation causes cellular stress, osmotic imbalance, and oxidative damage, contributing to diabetic complications such as neuropathy, retinopathy, and nephropathy.^{10, 11}

Fig 1. Polyol pathway

Aldose reductase inhibitors (ARIs) work by blocking the activity of this enzyme, thereby reducing sorbitol buildup and preventing related cellular damage. Targeting the polyol pathway, ARIs help mitigate chronic diabetic complications, making them an important therapeutic strategy in diabetes management.¹¹ The structures of marketed ARIs are given in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Marketed aldose reductase inhibitors

<p>Tolrestat</p>		
<p>Zenarestat</p>		

While ARIs have shown promise in preclinical and clinical studies, their use is still under investigation, with ongoing research focused on enhancing their efficacy and reducing side effects. Considering this, a few thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogs (**1-50**) structures were designed. Their *in silico* properties were determined by various computational tools to predict physicochemical properties, bioactivity, *in silico* binding affinity and toxicity profiles in the present investigation.

METHODOLOGY

Selection of compounds

A few thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogs (**1-50**) structures were designed considering the pharmacophoric requirements of aldose reductase inhibitor (Epalrestat) and glitazone class of antidiabetic agents. The structural details were provided in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Structure and IUPAC names of designed compounds

Code	Structure	IUPAC Name
1.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide 4-hydroxyphenylalanine
2.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide (2S,3R)-2-Amino-3-hydroxybutanoic acid

3.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide (2S,3S)-2-Amino-3-methylpentanoic acid
4.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide Pyrididine-2-carboxylic acid
5.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide 2-Aminobutanedioic acid
6.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide
7.		2-{4-[(E)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}-4-methylpentanamide
8.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide 2-Amino-4-(methylthio)butanoic acid
9.		2-{4-[(E)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}butanediamide

10.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide (2S)-2-Amino-3-hydroxypropanoic acid
11.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide (S)-2-Amino-5-guanidinopentanoic acid
12.		2-{4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}-3-phenylpropanamide
13.		N-carbamoyl-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
14.		2-{4-[(E)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}pentanediamide
15.		6-amino-2-{3-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}hexanamide

16.		[[4-[(2)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]phenyl sulfonamide]amino]acetic acid
17.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide 2-(1H-Imidazol-4-yl)ethanamine
18.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfo-N-(2-amino-3-methylbutane)
19.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- sulfonamide (2S)-2-Amino-3-(1H-indol-3-yl)propanoic acid
20.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfo-N-(2-amino-3-sulfanylpropanamide)
21.		4-[(E)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-N-methylbenzene-1-sulfonamide

22.		4-[(<i>E</i>)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]- <i>N</i> -ethylbenzene-1-sulfonamide
23.		<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-[(<i>E</i>)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
24.		<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-[(<i>E</i>)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]4-chloro benzene-1-sulfonamide
25.		<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-[(<i>E</i>)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]3-chloro benzene-1-sulfonamide
26.		<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-[(<i>E</i>)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]4-flouro benzene-1-sulfonamide
27.		<i>N</i> -(4-Chlorophenyl)-4-[(<i>E</i>)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
28.		4-[(<i>E</i>)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-Thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-sulfonamide 2-Aminopentanedioic acid

29.		N-Butyl-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
30.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-N-(4-fluorophenyl)benzene-1-sulfonamide
31.		N-(4-Acetylphenyl)-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
32.		N-(4-Acetylphenyl)-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]pyrimidine-2-one-1-sulfonamide
33.		N-(4-Bromophenyl)-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide

34.		4-{4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}benzoic acid
35.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-N-(4-hydroxyphenyl)benzene-1-sulfonamide
36.		4-{4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}benzene-4-amino-3-methyl
37.		4-{4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido}naphthalene
38.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-N-(quinolin-5-yl)benzene-1-sulfonamide

39.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfo-N-(4-sulfonyl aniline)
40.		N-Butyl-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
41.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-N-phenylbenzene-1-sulfonamide
42.		N-Benzyl-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
43.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)benzene-1-sulfonamide

44.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-Dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]-N-(4-nitrophenyl)benzene-1-sulfonamide
45.		N-(4-Aminophenyl)-4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamide
46.		4-[(Z)-(2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-5-ylidene)methyl]benzene-1-sulfonamido(3-chloroisoquinoline-6-yl)
47.		4-[(Z)-(2,5-Dioxoimidazolidin-4-ylidene)methyl]-N-[(1Z)-ethylidene]benzene-1-sulfonamide

48.		4-[(Z)-(2,5-Dioxoimidazolidin-4-ylidene)methyl]-N-[(1E)-ethylidene]benzene-1-sulfonamide
49		4-[(Z)-(2,5-Dioxoimidazolidin-4-ylidene)benzene]-N-[(1E)-ethylidene]benzene-1-sulfonamide
50		(5Z)-5-benzylidene-1,3-oxazolidin-2,4-dione sulfo 1-phenylmethanimine

Prediction of physicochemical properties:

Physicochemical properties of the designed thiazolidine analogue drugs (1-50) were determined by online tools, such as Molinspiration web JME editor¹² and SwissADME¹³. Properties like molecular weight (MW), log P, hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA), hydrogen bond donors (HBD), molar volume (MV) were computed by using Molinspiration tool, while bioavailability and synthetic accessibility scores were determined using SwissADME.

Prediction of bioactivity studies: Bioactivity is predicted by molinspiration, is a measure of the ability of the drug molecule to interact with different receptors, such as GPCR ligands, Kinase inhibitors, Protease inhibitors, Ion channel modulators, or to interact with enzymes and

nuclear receptors. Larger the bioactivity score, higher is the probability that the proposed molecules will be active.¹²

Prediction of toxicity: Toxicity prediction of the designed thiazolidine analogue drugs (1-50) drugs was attempted by using OSIRIS property explorer and pkCSM tools.¹⁵ Toxicity parameters, such as mutagenicity, irritancy, tumorigenicity and reproductivity of the selected antiviral drugs were predicted using OSIRIS property explorer software. pkCSM is a machine learning platform which is useful for ADMT predictions. Parameters like maximum recommended tolerated dose (MRTD), lethal dosage (LD₅₀), hepatotoxicity, skin sensitization and T. Pyriformis toxicity of the compounds, 1-50 were predicted using pkCSM tool.

In silico molecular docking studies: Docking simulations of the designed thiazolidine analogue drugs (**1-50**) drugs was performed by using CB Dock¹⁵. Several target proteins were explored

initially in Protein data bank¹⁶. Based on the resolution and year of release a few proteins were considered for docking studies. The details were given in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Details of target proteins

S. No.	PDB ID	Resolution (Å)	Year of release	Co-crystallised ligand
1	1US0	0.66	2004	NADPH Dihydro-Nicotinamide-Adenine-Dinucleotide Phosphate
2	2ITY	3.2	2007	Gefitinib
3	1PWM	0.92	2004	Fidarestat
4	1ABN	2.40	1994	NADPH Dihydro-Nicotinamide-Adenine-Dinucleotide Phosphate
5	1PWL	1.10	2004	Minalrestat

Molecular docking involves following steps:

Step 1: Protein preparation

The X-ray crystal structure of the protein was downloaded from the RCSB protein data bank. The protein structure was modified in Biovia discovery studio¹⁷ by removing unwanted chains, water molecules The processed protein was then saved as *.pdb file (1PWM.pdb).

Step 2: Docking using CB Dock

CB-Dock was opened in the web browser. The 'Dock' option was selected. The required files (Protein file in PDB format and ligand file in MOL or PDB format) were selected for docking. The docked complexes were saved in .pdb file format.

Step 3: Visualization using Biovia

The complex files in .pdb format were selected to visualize the ligand interactions with the target protein. The detailed results were presented in the next section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Various in silico techniques were utilized to predict the physicochemical properties, bioactivity

scores, and toxicity parameters of the designed thiazolidinedione analogs (**1-50**).

Drug-likeness evaluation

Molecular properties of the designed thiazolidine-2,4-diones (**1-50**) were computed using Molinspiration and SwissADME online software tools. The properties such as MW, HBD, HBA, log P, TPSA, MV, RB were computed using Molinspiration, The details are provided in **Table 4**. The MWs of the compounds were in the range of 293.30-515.59 (< 500 daltons, except compound **39**), log P in the range of -0.94-3.28 (≤ 5), HBA in the range of 6-10 (≤ 10) and HBD in the range of 1-8 (≤ 5 , except compounds **2, 9, 11, 14** and **15**). Evaluation of selected compounds for RO5 revealed that all compounds are in compliance with rule of thumb except **2, 9, 11, 14, 15, 39**. The TPSA, MV and RB explain the intestinal absorption and pharmacodynamic nature of the molecules in BioPhase. The compound showed TPSA in the range of 96.10-184.03 and RB in the range of 3-10 indicating their possible good permeability in the cellular membranes.

Table 4. Drug-likeness properties of designed compounds

Code	Log P	TPSA	MW	HBA	HBD	violation	n rot b	Volume	Drug likeness	Drug score
1	1.6	159.42	447	9	5	0	7	356.28	8.06	0.73
2	0.51	171.45	400.44	10	6	1	7	313.86	4.51	0.37
3	2.02	139.20	411.50	8	4	0	8	343.60	5.74	0.45
4	0.40	142.43	396.45	9	4	0	5	312.40	6.24	0.37
5	-0.65	176.50	399.41	10	5	0	7	303.85	7.29	0.84

6	-0.38	176.50	413.43	10	5	0	8	365	6.08	0.87
7	1.48	139.20	397.48	8	4	0	7	326.80	7.24	0.88
8	0.60	139.20	415.52	8	4	0	8	328.34	2.84	0.84
9	0.03	182.29	398.42	10	6	1	7	307.12	3.22	0.87
10	-0.82	159.42	371.40	9	5	0	6	284.87	2.66	0.88
11	0.10	184.03	438.54	10	8	1	10	365.19	7.59	0.83
12	1.47	130.41	417.47	8	3	0	5	331.81	7.70	0.84
13	-0.17	139.20	327.34	8	4	0	3	243.22	6.38	0.94
14	-0.90	182.29	412.45	10	6	1	8	323.93	6.18	0.87
15	-0.32	165.22	412.49	9	6	1	9	338.55	5.86	0.88
16	-1.23	167.88	421.46	10	5	0	6	329.09	1.45	0.79
17	-0.92	139.20	355.40	8	4	0	4	276.61	2.57	0.89
18	-0.14	139.20	383.45	8	4	0	5	310.00	-0.01	0.67
19	0.69	154.99	470.53	9	5	0	6	377.24	4.34	0.78
20	-0.94	139.20	387.46	8	4	0	5	294.51	0.72	0.75
21	0.55	96.10	298.35	6	2	0	3	229.51	4.46	0.9
22	0.93	96.10	312.37	6	2	0	4	246.31	4.88	0.88
23	1.95	96.10	374.44	6	2	0	5	301.16	5.09	0.76
24	2.99	96.10	408.89	6	2	0	5	314.70	6.31	0.65
25	2.90	96.10	394.86	6	2	0	4	297.89	5.08	0.62
26	2.11	96.10	392.43	6	2	0	5	306.09	4.62	0.72
27	2.93	96.10	394.86	6	2	0	4	297.89	5.79	0.62
28	-0.33	128.78	380.41	9	2	0	4	290.50	7.55	0.90
29	1.43	96.10	326.40	6	2	0	5	263.12	5.02	0.89
30	2.41	96.10	378.41	6	2	0	4	289.29	3.93	0.88
31	2.15	113.17	402.45	7	2	0	5	319.90	4.12	0.52
32	1.49	103.76	374.45	7	2	0	4	301.91	5.67	0.90
33	3.06	96.10	439.31	6	2	0	4	302.24	3.21	0.79
34	1.35	130.24	424.24	8	2	0	5	318.41	4.12	0.86
35	1.77	116.33	376.42	7	3	0	4	292.38	5.21	0.89
36	2.11	122.12	389.46	7	4	0	4	312.21	-2.83	0.10
37	3.28	113.17	452.51	7	2	0	5	363.89	3.72	0.37
38	2.23	108.99	411.46	7	2	0	4	324.19	3.84	0.50
39	2.17	156.27	515.59	9	4	1	6	398.49	6.44	0.71
40	1.99	96.10	340.43	6	2	0	6	276.92	3.18	0.90
41	2.25	96.10	360.42	6	2	0	4	284.36	4.72	0.90
42	1.95	96.10	374.44	6	2	0	5	301.16	2.74	0.82
43	2.31	103.34	390.44	7	2	0	5	309.90	3.94	0.87
44	2.21	141.93	405.41	9	2	0	5	307.69	-5.96	0.44
45	1.32	122.12	375.43	7	4	0	4	295.65	2.90	0.20
46	2.75	96.97	445.92	6	1	0	4	342.13	3.81	0.63
47	0.26	112.23	293.30	7	2	0	3	234.64	-11.75	0.38
48	0.26	112.23	293.30	7	2	0	3	234.64	3.03	0.74
49	1.48	112.23	355.38	7	2	0	4	289.49	-0.05	0.39
50	1.58	109.58	356.36	7	2	0	4	286.07	-14.58	0.27

Prediction of bioactivity studies

The bioactivity data determined using molinspiration and the bioavailability score and synthetic accessibility score determined from

SwissADME tools were given in **Table 5**. The GPCR ligand activity of **1**, Ion channel modulation activity of **1** and kinase inhibitor activity of **16** was found to be significant among the tested Aldose

reductase inhibitor drugs. The highest Protease inhibition was observed in compounds **5**, **15** and **20**. The enzyme inhibitory activity of **16** was evidenced through *in silico* predictions as its shown the highest value (0.42) among all. The poor bioavailability of **39** is observed in the predictions, which may be due to its high molecular weight and Log P values. The significance of the synthetic accessibility score is

to determine the ease of synthesis of compounds. The scale ranges from 1-10. The value towards 1 denotes that the compound can be easily synthesized and the value approaching to 10 denotes that its difficulty in the synthesis. The predicted synthetic accessibility data are in the range of 2.97-4.43. The ease of synthesis of **47** was evidenced in the predictions, as its score showed the least value (2.97) among all.

Table 5. Bioactivity and bioavailability and synthetic accessibility data predicted for designed compounds (1- 50)

Code	GPCR Ligand	Ion channel modulator	Kinase inhibitor	Nuclear receptor ligand	Protease inhibitor	Enzyme inhibitor	Bioavail ability Score	Synthetic accessibility
1	-0.17	-0.16	-0.20	-0.23	0.12	-0.11	0.55	4.03
2	-0.11	-0.85	-0.23	-0.19	0.21	0.18	0.55	4.23
3	-0.36	-0.84	-0.39	-0.48	0.09	-0.10	0.55	4.43
4	-0.18	-0.96	-0.29	-0.25	-0.08	-0.04	0.55	4.08
5	-0.16	-0.77	-0.35	-0.28	0.22	0.03	0.11	3.87
6	-0.16	-0.76	-0.32	-0.24	-0.19	-0.04	0.11	3.92
7	-0.27	-0.81	-0.35	-0.38	0.17	-0.09	0.55	4.06
8	-0.38	-0.97	-0.61	-0.52	0.10	-0.03	0.55	4.20
9	-0.33	-0.94	-0.31	-0.44	0.10	-0.12	0.55	4.01
10	-0.25	-0.86	-0.20	-0.36	0.16	-0.02	0.55	4.01
11	-0.12	-0.58	-0.24	-0.65	-0.23	-0.03	0.55	3.33
12	-0.42	-0.82	-0.38	-0.68	-0.11	-0.20	0.55	3.52
13	-0.49	-0.88	-0.32	-0.63	-0.27	-0.03	0.55	3.15
14	-0.27	-0.83	-0.27	-0.39	-0.11	-0.07	0.55	4.00
15	-0.14	-0.69	-0.18	-0.38	0.22	0.02	0.55	4.12
16	0.24	-0.30	0.12	-0.79	0.32	0.42	0.55	3.90
17	-0.17	-0.82	-0.16	-0.53	-0.00	0.13	0.55	3.00
18	-0.17	-0.77	-0.17	-0.49	0.14	0.11	0.55	3.96
19	0.12	-0.42	0.07	-0.29	0.14	0.20	0.55	4.05
20	-0.12	-0.77	-0.05	-0.43	0.32	0.42	0.55	3.86
21	-0.73	-1.04	-0.37	-0.60	-0.56	-0.23	0.55	3.06
22	-0.64	-1.08	-0.49	-0.64	-0.48	-0.18	0.55	3.16
23	-0.41	-0.78	-0.26	-0.40	-0.25	-0.10	0.55	3.38
24	-0.40	-0.76	-0.27	-0.40	-0.29	-0.13	0.55	3.35
25	-0.46	-0.86	-0.28	-0.36	-0.38	-0.23	0.55	3.27
26	-0.39	-0.76	-0.22	-0.36	-0.27	-0.12	0.55	3.36
27	-0.45	-0.80	-0.29	-0.35	-0.35	-0.20	0.55	3.23
28	-0.42	-0.73	-0.25	-0.30	-0.26	-0.15	0.55	3.61
29	-0.47	-0.96	-0.39	-0.46	-0.36	-0.13	0.55	3.23
30	-0.44	-0.81	-0.24	-0.30	-0.34	-0.19	0.55	3.21
31	-0.49	-0.81	-0.40	-0.38	-0.36	-0.23	0.55	3.33
32	-0.41	-0.71	-0.30	-0.47	-0.36	-0.17	0.55	3.89
33	-0.54	-0.87	-0.31	-0.44	-0.42	-0.24	0.55	3.27
34	-0.40	-0.75	-0.29	-0.17	-0.26	-0.10	0.11	3.27
35	-0.40	-0.75	-0.23	-0.19	-0.30	-0.12	0.55	3.22

36	-0.45	-0.78	-0.17	-0.43	-0.30	-0.15	0.55	3.43
37	-0.37	-0.71	-0.23	-0.27	-0.26	-0.13	0.55	3.55
38	-0.29	-0.61	-0.01	-0.27	-0.24	-0.04	0.55	3.32
39	-0.24	-0.48	-0.17	-0.35	-0.15	-0.03	0.55	3.79
40	-0.42	-0.91	-0.35	-0.39	-0.29	-0.10	0.55	3.32
41	-0.46	-0.83	-0.28	-0.34	-0.33	-0.18	0.55	3.26
42	-0.41	-0.78	-0.26	-0.40	-0.25	-0.10	0.55	3.47
43	-0.47	-0.84	-0.30	-0.33	-0.36	-0.21	0.55	3.27
44	-0.55	-0.78	-0.39	-0.39	-0.41	-0.25	0.55	3.37
45	-0.40	-0.73	-0.17	-0.37	-0.22	-0.07	0.55	3.34
46	-0.32	-0.79	0.01	-0.25	-0.15	0.05	0.55	3.31
47	-0.46	-1.30	-0.48	-1.27	-0.78	-0.37	0.55	2.97
48	-0.46	-1.30	-0.48	-1.27	-0.78	-0.37	0.55	2.98
49	-0.46	-1.17	-0.38	-1.02	-0.68	-0.43	0.55	3.28
50	-0.54	-0.74	-0.52	-0.33	-0.56	-0.09	0.55	3.13

Toxicity prediction

The toxicity predictions determined for the selected drugs using OSIRIS property explorer and pKCSM tools were provided in **Table 6**. The toxicity scores predicted by Osiris property explorer were color-coded, where green indicates

probable activity. Properties with high risks of undesired/toxic effects such as mutagenicity, tumorigenic, etc are shown in red, the compounds with mild toxic effects are indicated as orange, while the drugs with low probability of such effects are indicated as green color.

Table 6. Toxicity data predictions using Osiris property explorer and pKCSM tools

Code	Mutagenic	Tumorigenic	Irritant	Reproductive effect	LD ₅₀	Hepato toxicity	Skin sensitivity	T. pyriformis toxicity
1	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.98	Yes	No	0.301
2	Red	Orange	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
3	Green	Orange	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
4	Rede	Orange	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
5	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
6	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
7	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
8	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
9	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.051	Yes	No	0.283
10	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.051	yes	No	0.283
11	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	Yes	0.285
12	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.353	Yes	No	0.353
13	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
14	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
15	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.164	Yes	No	0.349
16	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.781	Yes	No	0.285
17	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.519	Yes	No	0.476
18	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.014	Yes	No	0.319
19	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.578	Yes	No	0.308
20	Green	Green	Green	Green	3.606	Yes	No	0.866
21	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.362	Yes	No	0.645

22	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
23	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
24	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
25	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
26	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
27	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.198	Yes	No	0.515
28	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.93	Yes	No	0.338
29	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
30	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.207	Yes	No	0.451
31	Red	Green	Green	Green	2.059	Yes	No	0.382
32	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.846	Yes	No	0.93
33	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.211	Yes	No	0.512
34	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.482	No	No	0.285
35	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.921	Yes	No	0.405
36	Red	Red	Green	Red	2.482	No	No	0.285
37	Orange	Red	Green	Green	2.065	Yes	No	0.296
38	Red	Green	Green	Green	2.582	Yes	No	0.329
39	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.481	Yes	No	0.285
40	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.434	Yes	No	0.774
41	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.04	Yes	No	1.04
42	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.04	Yes	No	0.502
43	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.005	Yes	No	0.404
44	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.47	Yes	No	0.323
45	Red	Orange	Orange	Red	1.742	Yes	No	0.364
46	Orange	Green	Green	Green	2.097	Yes	No	0.36
47	Green	Orange	Green	Green	2.04	Yes	No	2.524
48	Green	Orange	Red	Green	1.714	Yes	No	0.261
49	Green	Green	Red	Green	2.016	Yes	No	0.388
50	Green	Green	Red	Green	2.04	Yes	No	0.312

In silico Docking studies

The potential affinities of thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogs (1-50) towards Aldose reductase was studied by docking studies using CB-Dock and Biovia software using 1PWM and 1PWL as the target proteins. The marketed Aldose reductase inhibitor Fidarestat for 1PWM and Minalrestat for 1PWL were considered as a reference compound and the binding interactions and binding energies of the designed compounds were compared with that of Fidarestat and Minalrestat. The results were

given in Table 8 and 9. The reference compound Fidarestat has shown binding energy of -8.7 Kcal and was found to interact with amino acid residues TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300 of the target protein. The reference compound Minalrestat has shown binding energy of -9.5 Kcal and was found to interact with amino acid residues TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300 of the target protein. These interactions were thought to be important to identify the potential ligands.

Table 8. Docking results of the thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogues (1-50) with 1PWM

Code	Binding energy (Kcal)	Contact residues
Fidarestat	-8.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
1	-10.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
2	-9.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300

3	-9.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
4	-9.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
5	-9.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
6	-8.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
7	-8.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
8	-8.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
9	-8.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
10	-9.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
11	-9.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
12	-11.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
13	-8.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
14	-9.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
15	-8.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
16	-10.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
17	-8.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
18	-10.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
19	-11.1	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
20	-8.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
21	-9.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
22	-8.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
23	-10.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
24	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
25	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
26	-10.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
27	-9.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
28	-10.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
29	-9.1	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
30	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
31	-10.8	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
32	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
33	-10.5	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
34	-10.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
35	-10.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
36	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
37	-10.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
38	-10.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
39	-11.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
40	-8.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
41	-9.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
42	-10.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
43	-9.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
44	-10.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
45	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
46	-11.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
47	-9.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
48	-9.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
49	-12.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
50	-11.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300

Table 9. Docking results of the thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogues (1-50) with 1PWL

Code	Binding energy (Kcal)	Contact residues
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1	-11.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
2	-9.5	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
3	-9.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
4	-9.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
5	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
6	-9.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
7	-9.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
8	-8.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
9	-9.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
10	-9.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
11	-10.8	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
12	-10.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
13	-9.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
14	-9.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
15	-9.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
16	-10.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
17	-9.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
18	-10.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
19	-12.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
20	-9.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
21	-8.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
22	-8.3	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
23	-11.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
24	-11.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
25	-11.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
26	-12.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
27	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
28	-10.4	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
29	-9.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
30	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
31	-10.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
32	-10.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
33	-10.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
34	-10.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
35	-10.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
36	-10.8	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
37	-10.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
38	-10.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
39	-11.0	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
40	-8.8	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
41	-10.1	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
42	-11.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
43	-10.7	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
44	-10.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
45	-10.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
46	-12.5	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
47	-9.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
48	-9.9	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
49	-12.6	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300
50	-12.2	TRP20, TYR48, HIS110, TRP111, LEU300

Fig 2. Ligands interactions with 1PWM

Fig 3. Ligands interactions with 1PWL

CONCLUSION

The present investigation involves designing and *in silico* studies fifty thiazolidine-2,4-dione analogues (**1-50**), which were designed by considering the pharmacophoric requirements of aldose reductase inhibitors. They were evaluated for various pharmacokinetic, biological and toxicological activity predictions using freely available online tools. Forty-five out of fifty compounds were found to obey RO5 indicating their better oral absorption. Among the designed compounds, the amino acid-coupled thiazolidine-2,4-diones have shown significant bioactivity in the *in silico* predictions. The GPCR ligand activity and kinase inhibitor activity of **16** was found to be superior among all. Highest Protease inhibition was observed for **5**, **15**, **25**. The properties evaluated by SwissADME, i.e., The synthetic accessibility score and bioavailability scores of the compounds were found to be satisfactory. The potential affinity of designed molecules towards aldose reductase isoforms (PDB IDs: 1PWM and 1PWL) was evaluated by performing docking studies. The *in-silico* aldose reductase affinity of amino acid-coupled thiazolidine-2,4-diones (**1**, **12**, **16**, **19**) was found to be high among all compounds. The knowledge acquired about pharmacophoric requirements from these studies

will serve as a foundation for future design and synthesis of aldose reductase inhibitors.

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